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Relationship of Neuroticism Personality Trait with Transformational Leadership Style of Secondary School Administrators in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan

Dr. Asghar Ali

Ph.D (Education) Deputy Controller of Exams, The University of Haripur

Dr. Fazal Hakim

Ph.D (Education) Lecturer Department of Education, The University of Haripur

Dr. Noreen Ayaz

Ph.D (Education) Principal Government Girls Higher Secondary School Dingi Haripur

Dr. Irum Jabeen

Ph.D (Education) Principal Government Girls Higher Secondary School Kangra, Haripur

Mr. Shahid Ali Khan

BS Journalism and Mass Communication, University of Peshawar

ABSTRACT

The study explores the magnitude of neuroticism personality trait (NPT), degree of transformational leadership style (TLS), and relationship between NPT and sub-factors of NPT with TLS. 640 school administrators were selected from the population. Multi multistage stratified random sampling technique was used in the selection of samples. NPT and TLS questionnaires were used for the purpose of data collection. Mean, standard deviation and Pearson correlation coefficient were used to analyze the data. Means were compared with the t test statistic, and ANOVA was used for the interaction effect of gender and school sector. Concluded from the results of the study that TLS has a statistically significant and strong negative correlation with NPT and their sub factors. Gender-wise statistically significant difference does not exist in the means score of NPT and TLS. The school sector-wise statistically significant differences exist in the means score of NPT at the 0.05 level of significance and do not exist in the means score of TLS. Gender and sector-wise interaction effect on TLS is statistically significance does not exist on the means score and Gender and school sector-wise interaction effect on NPT is statistically significance exist in the means score at 0.05 level of significance.

Key words: Neuroticism Personality Trait, Transformational Leadership Style, Secondary School Administrators, sub factors of Neuroticism Personality Trait

Introduction

This study examines the relationship between the neuroticism personality trait of secondary school administrators and their transformational leadership style in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.

To promote an ideal learning environment, school leaders/ Principals are tasked to manage several components of school and must lead the teachers (Schneider and Burton, 2001). Hanbury, (2001) stated that motivating of followers, establishment of goals, objectives and vision for the institutes, give decision making powers to the followers and create collaboration with other sister institutes are mainly dependent on leader style of leadership.

[Connelly \(2008\)](#), stated that the responsibilities of school administrators is happen to be very much difficult, the school administrators requiring shows courage, vision, and the skill that support conducive learning environment for the teacher, students and adults. According to [Connelly \(2008\)](#) the secondary school administrators must possess the qualities transformational leader as school administrators visualize the future, work for it, and lead their subordinates for the positive change in the society.

The Tukey's research shows that teachers who are teaching experience is in the range of 1 to 10 years were statistically more significant differences then the teachers with experiences I the range of more than 21 years of experience ([Karaköse, 2008](#))

Transformational Leaders as Administrators

The transformational leadership theory does not completely represent the leadership but only represents some particular ideas that were observed in the behavior of leadership (Avolio, 1999). According to [Connelly \(2008\)](#), the secondary school administrators must possess the qualities transformational leader as school administrators visualize the future, work for it, and lead their subordinates for the positive change in the society.

According to Smith and Bell (2011) an individual will be a transformational leader if he/she has the ability to encourage, influence, to motivate his/her followers, and most importantly they can shape the attitudes of their followers according to the surrounding environment. A transformational leader encourages their followers by showing positivity, encouraging them to achieve their common objectives, promising to their mentors, and a strong and unshakable belief in the upcoming events in near future (Smith and Bell, 2011). Tejada et al. (2001) stated that transformational leaders are always positive and always help their followers for the achievement of the desired objectives. According to Bass (2000) for the improvement of schools, visionary transformational leadership is essential. Decisions of the administration are depending on leadership practices; therefore, the style of leadership defines the direction of an organization (Walumbwa et al., 2007). Nowadays leadership studies emphasize maximum on team oriented methods and minimum on the hierarchical method (Bass, 1999).

Neuroticism Personality Trait (NPT) and School's Leaders

According to Berr et al. (2000), neuroticism in leadership is characterized by a leader's level of stress tolerance or psychological adjustment. Leaders exhibiting neurotic traits tend to demonstrate anxious behavior and thought patterns, often associated with heightened worry and stress (McCrae, 1987). Secondary school heads displaying neuroticism thoughts may demons fluctuating levels of self-confidence, which can affect the way they inspire achievement among their team fellows (Avolio et al., 1995).

School heads with neuroticism qualities are most of the time connected to illogical beliefs and sensitive to insecurity (Barlow et al., 2014). Principals who exhibit such traits may set high goals and values for their group members and encourage them to challenge conventional norms (Bridbord & De-Lucia-Waack, 2011). Furthermore, leaders with neurotic characteristics have the potential to serve as role models, motivating their followers and instilling assurance in their leadership abilities (Cranston et al., 2004).

These leaders are frequently described as volatile and inconsistent (Zhang & Huang, 2001). In some cases, principals with neurotic traits may cause their team members to lose trust in their leadership. In contrast, leaders who do not possess neurotic traits tend to be emotionally stable and secure (Judge & Bono, 2000a). Such leaders are generally less affected by stress and exhibit a greater ability to manage stressful situations matched to neuroticism leaders (Zhang & Huang, 2001). School heads with low neuroticism are often more confident in their decisions and maintain clearer thinking compared to those with higher levels of neuroticism (Gosling et al., 2003). These leaders are also more likely to make balanced decisions, remain composed, and foster a calmer organizational atmosphere (Ehrhart et al., 2009). Additionally, leaders with

emotional stability are often seen as more empathetic and respectful toward their team members (Bruk-Lee, 2009).

Figure 1: Aspects of Neuroticism
The Neurotic and Transformational Leaders in School Administration

The neuroticism personality traits closely affect one’s behavior, how individuals make their decision and how individuals observe the environment (Myers-Briggs and McCaully, 1985). When school leaders are aware of transformational leadership and neurotic personality, they can lead more effectively. Their abilities are enhanced, and they gain a better understanding of how a leader's behavior influences decision-making (Hautula,

2005). The theory of transformational leadership stresses to empowering and encouraging teachers to work together with the management, to develop policies and educational goals for the school. Now school teachers and employees have the opportunities to contribute to the achievements of the school and confidently play their role on campus which must be appreciated by the school administrators (Kruger et al., 2007). Transformational leadership is the main component of the success of secondary school (Hallinger and Heck, 1999). Effective educational leaders have the ability to put together the right people as a team and they are working together, are productive, and create collaboration (Hurrion, 2006).

In the educational setting within schools, the School administrators can play the lead role and provide (Hautala, 2005). Respect their teacher, arrangement of training for professional and personal development, regular meetings with a community partners and listening to their problems, and building of respectable environment are the main responsibilities of school administrators (Gordon and Patterson, 2006).

According to Brown et al. (2008) the motivation to shine of school administrators is directly proportional to the independence, gratitude, and achievement of goals. Many of research studies were conducted on neuroticism personality traits, transformational leadership styles and its relationship, indicating the negative correlation between the both (Larsen and Buss, 2005).

The objectives of the study are given below.

1. To explore the magnitude of the neuroticism personality trait and the degree of transformational leadership style, as well as their relationship, among secondary school administrators in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.
2. To explore the differences in the neuroticism personality trait and transformational leadership style based on gender and school sector among secondary school administrators in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.
3. To investigate the interaction effects of gender and school sector on the neuroticism personality trait and the level of transformational leadership style among secondary school administrators in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan.

Methodology

Quantitative method of research strategy was applied in the current research study. Salvador, J. T. (2016) *defined the* quantitative research is the systematic pragmatic examination of obvious phenomena through statistical techniques, mathematical techniques or computational techniques.

Population of the Study

The study's population comprises secondary school administrators in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, a province in northern Pakistan. The province spans 101,741 km², with a population of approximately 35 million, comprising 52% males and 48% females, accounting for 11.9% of Pakistan's total population (Khyber Pakhtunkhwa Government Website).

Administratively, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa is divided into 36 districts, which are further clustered into five zones by the Public Service Commission of Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. The commission serves as the province's hiring organization.

Zone-wise Distribution of Districts:

Zones	Zone 1	Zone 2	Zone 3	Zone 4	Zone 5
Districts	1. Orakzai 2. North Waziristan 3. South Waziristan 4. Khyber 5. Bajaur 6. Kurram 7. Mohmand 8. Some parts of the Frontier Region connected to Peshawar, Kohat, Bannu, and Dera Ismail Khan districts	1. Mardan 2. Peshawar 3. Nowshera 4. Charsadda 5. Swabi.	1. Dir Upper 2. Dir Lower 3. Shangla, 4. Kohistan, 5. Malakand, 6. Chitral, 7. Swat 8. Buner, 9. Battagram 10. Some parts of Haripur, Abbottabad, and Mansehra districts	1. Dera Ismail Khan, 2. Tank, 3. Bannu, 4. Lakki 5. Marwat 6. Kohat 7. Karak.	1. Haripur 2. Abbottabad, 3. Mansehra, 4. Certain areas not covered in Zone 3.

According to the Annual Census School Report (2020-21), there are 5322 public (educational institutions that are funded and operated by government authorities) and (educational institutions that are privately funded and operated) private secondary school administrators in Zones 2 and 5. The report reveals that 49.5% of administrators employed in government funded schools, while 50.5% employed in privately funded schools. The same report indicates that 53.4% of secondary school administrators in Zones 2 and 5 are male, while 46.6% are female. Additionally, 62.7% of administrators are from rural areas, while 37.3% are from urban areas. The table below shows the percentage distribution of school heads by district.

Percentage distribution of school heads by district..

District\ Percentage	Peshawar	Charsadda	Mardan	Swabi	Nowshera	Haripur	Abbottabad	Mansehra	Total %
% Of Male School Administrators	52.2	50	48.4	49.5	59.2	60.5	48.7	59	53.4
% Of Female School	47.8	50	51.6	50.5	40.8	39.5	51.3	41	46.6

Administrators									
% Of Public School Administrators	39.4	56.6	49	46	43.8	49.8	46.8	58.3	49.5
% Of Private School Administrators	61.6	43.4	51	54	56.3	50.2	53.2	41.7	50.5
% Of Rural School Administrators	51.3	67.9	73.1	63.7	39.2	77.8	70	60	62.7
% Of Urban School Administrators	48.7	32.1	26.9	36.3	60.8	22.2	30	40	37.3

Sample for the Study

For collection of quantitative data from population, multi-stage stratified random sampling technique was used. Target population was selected through simple random sampling, two zones, Zone 2 and Zone 5, was selected from the five zones as target population.

The sampled population was then divided into homogeneous groups within each district, considering factors such as government public schools administrators and private schools administrators, urban area schools administrators and rural area schools administrators, and gender (male and female school administrators). Stratified random sampling was used to ensure that a large number of sample units were randomly selected, offering an equal probability of selection for each school heads within the target population (Tashakkori & Teddlie, 2003). This method was chosen for its ability to reduce sampling error and ensure equal representation across different strata.

The sample size was calculated based on a 4% margin of error and a 95% confidence interval. Zone 5 consists of three districts: Haripur, Abbottabad, and Mansehra, while Zone 2 includes five districts: Charsadda, Mardan, Nowshera, Swabi, and Peshawar. In each district, 80 secondary school administrators were randomly selected, with 40 secondary school administrators from the government public schools and 40 secondary school administrators from the private schools.

In total, 640 secondary school administrators were randomly chosen, with equal representation from both the government public secondary school administrators and private secondary school administrators (50% each). Additionally, the sample was balanced by gender, with 50% male and 50% female administrators from both sectors.

Table of Sample Composition

Gender	Male (320 Schools Administrators)	Female(320 Schools Administrators)	50 Percent
Sector	Public (320 Schools Administrators)	Private (320 Schools Administrators)	50 Percent
Location	Rural (320 Schools Administrators)	Urban (320 Schools Administrators)	50 Percent
Zone	Zone 2 (320 Schools Administrators)	Zone 5 (320 Schools Administrators)	Zone 2(62.5 Percent) Zone 5(37.5 Percent)

Tree Diagram of Sampling Distribution

DEVELOPMENT, VALIDITY AND RELIABILITY OF TOOL OF TRANSFORMATIONAL LEADERSHIP STYLE

A questionnaire was designed to assess the leadership style of secondary school administrators, specifically focusing on aspects of transformational leadership. The questionnaire consisted of 28 items, which were reviewed by experts, including education professors and practicing school administrators, to gather feedback and ensure validity.

After pilot testing, an item analysis was performed, and revisions were made based on the expert feedback and the results of the pilot testing. The final version of the questionnaire was then prepared for use in the study.

The questionnaire aimed to measure the transformational leadership style of secondary school administrators, using a Likert scale with options ranging from "not accurate" to "very accurate."

After incorporating revisions, the questionnaire was piloted to assess its reliability. The tool for measuring neuroticism as a personality trait among secondary school administrators was adapted based on expert guidance in educational psychology.

Content Validity of the Questioner of Leadership styles

Content validity has significant importance for any measurement and it indicates the relevancy of instrument to the learning environment and how it is related to the subjects under research study. Content validity is clarified as how the research instrument will assess the situation or subject under study regarding which conclusions are to be drawn. The Content validity can also have defined as it indicates the description of the universe of research items, out of which selection of item was made and also include the detail of the selection process.

Content validity can infer the process of selection sample data from statistical population. In the current study the researcher ensures the content validity of the questioner of leadership style, the questioner was sent to four experts in the field of education for comments. Some of the questions were modified as per expert's comments.

The tool used to measure the neuroticism factor of personality traits among secondary school administrators was selected based on recommendations from experts in the field of educational psychology. The neuroticism questionnaire was adopted from the International Personality Item Pool (IPIP) website (www.ipip.org.uk), a widely recognized resource for personality assessments. As this questionnaire is internationally accepted and frequently used for personality testing, no additional content validity was required for its adoption.

Items Statistic for Transformational Leadership Style Questioner

Transformational Leadership Style items	Sample Mean	Sample Standard Deviation	Cronbach's Alpha (if item deleted)
TLS1	2.80	.98135	.861
TLS2	2.79	.94187	.862
TLS3	2.83	.92354	.861
TLS4	2.81	.87443	.862
TLS5	2.89	.95598	.861
TLS6	2.98	.85304	.862
TLS7	2.82	.95796	.861

TLS8	2.71	1.10975	.862
TLS9	2.83	.91965	.862
TLS10	2.76	.83397	.862
TLS11	2.72	.98434	.861
TLS12	2.85	.94687	.862
TLS13	2.95	.92656	.861
TLS14	2.74	.87431	.862
TLS15	2.89	.95598	.861
TLS16	2.99	.85029	.862
TLS17	2.82	.95796	.861
TLS18	2.71	.9750	.862
TLS19	2.83	.91965	.862
TLS20	2.76	.83069	.862
TLS21	2.73	.98434	.861
TLS22	2.85	.94687	.862
TLS23	2.95	.92656	.861
TLS24	2.74	.87431	.862
TLS25	2.89	.95598	.861
TLS26	2.99	.85029	.862
TLS27	2.82	.95796	.861
TLS28	2.71	.97500	.862
Transformational Leadership style	2.83	2.2162	.819

The table above presents the mean responses for items related to the transformational leadership style, with scores ranging from 2.71 to 2.99. The overall mean is 2.83, and the scale mean is 2.65. Among the 65 questions, items 8, 18, and 28 had the lowest mean score of 2.71. These items pertain to taking risks in decision-making, implementing hierarchy, and encouraging staff.

In contrast, item 26 received the highest mean score of 2.99, which focuses on explaining the benefits of achieving work goals to staff. Item 8 showed the highest standard deviation, indicating a significant variation in secondary school administrators' opinions on taking risks in decision-making. Conversely, item 20 had the lowest standard deviation, suggesting minimal variation in administrators' views regarding the rigidity of imposing organizational structures.

The questionnaire demonstrated high reliability, with an overall Cronbach’s alpha of 0.919. All questions showed high reliability, indicating that all items related to the transformational leadership style were retained.

Item Statistics Neuroticism and Sub Scale of Neuroticism Test

Sub items if Neuroticism	Sample Mean	Sample Standard Deviation	Cronbach's Alpha (if item deleted)
Neuroticism Anxiety 1	2.73	.984	.894
Neuroticism Anxiety 2	2.85	.947	.901
Neuroticism Anxiety 3	2.95	.927	.897
Neuroticism Anxiety 4	2.74	.874	.898
Neuroticism Anger 1	2.90	.956	.894

Neuroticism Anger 2	2.99	.850	.900
Neuroticism Anger 3	2.83	.958	.895
Neuroticism Anger 4	2.71	1.011	.905
Neuroticism Depression 1	2.83	.920	.904
Neuroticism Depression 2	2.76	.834	.903
Neuroticism Depression 3	2.73	.984	.894
Neuroticism Depression 4	2.85	.947	.901
Neuroticism Immoderation 1	2.95	.927	.897
Neuroticism Immoderation 2	2.74	.874	.898
Neuroticism Immoderation 3	2.90	.956	.894
Neuroticism Immoderation 4	3.00	.850	.900
Neuroticism self-Consciousness 1	2.83	.958	.895
Neuroticism self-Consciousness 2	2.71	1.010	.905
Neuroticism self-Consciousness 3	2.83	.920	.904
Neuroticism self-Consciousness 4	2.76	.831	.903
Neuroticism vulnerability 1	2.73	.984	.894
Neuroticism vulnerability 2	2.85	.947	.901
Neuroticism vulnerability 3	2.95	.927	.897
Neuroticism vulnerability 4	2.74	.874	.898
Neuroticism	2.828	.831	.902

The table above presents the average response for questions related to the Neuroticism trait of personality, ranging from 2.71 to 3.00. The total mean of the subscale is 2.828, and the scale mean is 2.827 out of 120 items. Item Neuroticism Anger 4 received the lowest mean score of 2.71, which pertains to Neuroticism immoderation. In contrast, item Neuroticism Immoderation 4 achieved the highest mean score of 3.00.

Item Neuroticism Anger 4 exhibited the highest standard deviation in the Neuroticism Personality Trait, indicating a high level of variation in secondary school administrators' opinions regarding anger management, specifically the statement "Rarely get irritated." Conversely, item Neuroticism Anger 4 demonstrated the lowest standard deviation, showing a low level of variation in administrators' opinions on controlling cravings, a facet of Neuroticism immoderation.

The questionnaire exhibited high reliability, with an overall Cronbach's alpha of 0.902. All questions demonstrated high reliability, indicating that all items related to the Neuroticism Personality Trait were retained.

ANALYSIS OF DATA

Statistic of secondary school administrator’s magnitude of Neuroticism personality trait and degree of Transformational leadership.

Items	Sample Mean	Sample Standard Deviation	Sample Size(n)
Neuroticism	3.008	.0292	640
Transformational Leadership	3.99	2.73	640

Table above indicates that on the average in each question the mean score of neuroticism Factors of Personality 3.008 with standard deviation of 0.292, and on the average in each Transformational Leadership Style question the mean score 3.99 with standard deviation of 2.73.

Pearson Correlation Coefficients of Transformational leadership style with neuroticism and six Aspects of Neuroticism.

		Neuroticism	Anxiety	Anger	Depression	Self-consciousness	Immoderation	Vulnerability
Transformational leadership style	Pearson Correlation	-.797**	-.906**	-.916**	-.838**	-.932**	-.769**	-.906**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
	N	640	640	640	640	640	640	640

** Correlation is significant at P< .01

The table above reveals a strong negative correlation between the transformational leadership style and neuroticism, as well as its six aspects. This correlation is statistically significant at the 0.01 level. Additionally, all correlation coefficients between the six aspects of neuroticism and transformational leadership style are statistically significant (p < 0.01). The table shows that the correlation coefficients between the neuroticism factors and transformational leadership style vary, ranging from -0.769 for immoderation to -0.932 for self-consciousness. This indicates that different aspects of neuroticism have distinct relationships with the transformational leadership style.

t-test for Gender wise difference of Transformational leadership style

Means		Standard Deviations		t-Value	d.f	Significance (2 tailed)	Cohen's -d (Effect size)
Female	Male	Female	Male				
78.11	79.11	14.11	14.99	2.50	638	.647	.40

The table above presents the mean scores for transformational leadership style, with females scoring 78.11 and males scoring 79.89. The standard deviation for females is 14.11, while for males it is 14.99, indicating greater variation in transformational leadership styles among male administrators.

The two-tailed significance value of 0.647 exceeds 0.05, suggesting that no statistically significant difference exists in the mean scores of transformational leadership style between males and females.

The effect size, measured by Cohen's D, is 0.40, indicating a moderate effect size in transformational leadership style.

t-test for Gender wise difference of Neuroticism Personality Trait.

Means		Standard Deviations		t-Value	d.f	Significance (2 tailed)	Cohen's -D (Effect size)
Female	Male	Female	Male				
69.99	68.88	12.31	12.71	2.400	638	.5982	.416

The table above presents the average scores for the Neuroticism factor of Personality, with females scoring 69.99 and males scoring 68.88. The standard deviation for females is 12.31, while for males it is 12.71, indicating slightly greater variation in Neuroticism factors among male secondary school administrators.

The two-tailed significance value of 0.582 exceeds 0.05, suggesting that no statistically significant difference exists in the mean scores of Neuroticism factors between males and females.

To further elucidate the difference, Cohen's D effect size was calculated. The effect size, 0.416, indicates a modest effect size in Neuroticism factors.

t-test for Sector wise difference of Transformational leadership style

Means		Standard Deviations		t-Value	d.f	Significance (2 tailed)	Cohen's -D (Effect size)
Private	Public	Private	Public				
71.33	72.48	13.15	12.99	1.402	638	.503	.31

The table above presents the mean scores for Transformational leadership styles among private and public sector secondary school administrators. Private sector administrators scored 71.33, while public sector administrators scored 72.48. The standard deviation for private sector administrators was 13.15, whereas for public sector administrators it was 12.99. This indicates that public sector administrators exhibited less variation in their Transformational leadership styles compared to their public sector counterparts.

The two-tailed significance value of 0.503 exceeded 0.05, suggesting that no statistically significant difference existed in the mean scores of Transformational leadership styles between private and public sector administrators.

To further explore the difference, Cohen's D effect size was calculated. The effect size, 0.31, indicates a moderate effect size in Transformational leadership style.

Sector Wise Significant Difference in Neuroticism Personality Trait.

Means		Standard Deviations		t-Value	d.f	Significance (2 tailed)	Cohen's -D (Effect size)
Private	Public	Private	Public				
70.11	74.21	13.24	14.89	.246	638	.044	.37

The table above presents the average scores for Neuroticism Personality trait among private and public sector secondary school administrators. Private sector administrators scored 74.21, while public sector administrators scored 70.11. The standard deviation for private sector administrators was 14.89, whereas for public sector administrators it was 13.24. This indicates greater variation in Neuroticism Personality trait among private sector administrators.

The two-tailed significance value of 0.044 was less than 0.05, indicating a statistically significant difference in the mean scores of Neuroticism Personality trait between private and public sector administrators.

To further elucidate this difference, Cohen's D effect size was calculated. The effect size, 0.37, indicates a moderate effect size in Neuroticism factors of personality trait.

Interaction Effect of Gender and School Sector on Transformational leadership style and Neuroticism factor of personality.

Source	Dependent Variables	Mean Square	F	Sig
Gender*Sector	Neuroticism	.94	.952	.045
	Transformational leadership style	.9	.068	.494

The table above reveals the significance or critical values for the interaction effects of gender and sector on Transformational leadership style and Neuroticism. Specifically, the p-value for the interaction effect of gender

and sector on Transformational leadership style is 0.494, exceeding the significance level of 0.05. This indicates that no statistically significant interaction effect of gender and sector exists on Transformational leadership style.

In contrast, the p-value for the interaction effect of gender and sector on Neuroticism is 0.045, which is below the significance level. This suggests that a statistically significant interaction effect of gender and sector does exist on Neuroticism factors of personality.

DISCUSSION

This quantitative research study aimed to investigate the relationship among Neuroticism personality trait, aspects of Neuroticism personality, and Transformational leadership style of secondary school principals/administrators in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. To analyze the data, the researcher employed arithmetic mean to determine central tendency and standard deviation to measure dispersion. T-tests were used to examine statistical significance between variables, while Cohen's D was calculated to assess sample size effect. Correlation coefficients were employed to measure the degree of relationship. Additionally, ANOVA was used to investigate the interaction effect of gender and sector on dependent variables.

The study's findings revealed a strong negative correlation between Transformational leadership style and Neuroticism Personality trait, consistent with Simic et al.'s (2022) study. The results also indicated a statistically significant correlation between Neuroticism factors of personality traits and Transformational leadership style, aligning with Hassan et al.'s (2016) findings.

The study further found that Transformational leadership style exhibited a strong negative correlation with Neuroticism personality trait, aspects of Neuroticism, and correlation, which was statistically significant. These results are consistent with Adam's (2009) study. Moreover, all aspects of Neuroticism (Anxiety, Anger, Depression, Self-consciousness, Immoderation, and Vulnerability) were strongly negatively correlated with Transformational leadership style, and the correlation was statistically significant. These findings are in line with Barbuto Jr et al.'s (2010) study.

The study also concluded that there was no statistically significant difference in Neuroticism personality trait and Transformational leadership style among male and female secondary school administrators, confirming Trinidad and Normore's (2005) findings. However, the study found no statistically significant difference in Transformational leadership style among male and female administrators, which contrasts with Ch et al.'s (2017) findings.

Furthermore, the study investigated the interaction effect of gender and sector on Transformational leadership style and found no statistically significant interaction effect, consistent with Lin's (2012) findings. The study also examined the interaction effect of gender and sector on Neuroticism personality trait and found a statistically significant interaction effect, confirming Judge and Bono's (2000) findings.

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